

Beyond Tribal Affiliations for National Integration: An Example from 2 Samuel 5:1-5

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Abstract

Elders are significant members of every society. Their roles in their different societies are often invaluable. Without them a society or nation suffers. They can help to create social measures for detribalization and national growth through integration. The Old Testament is replete with innumerable events involving elders on issues of national relevance. The paper concentrates on the case of 2 Sam 5:1-5 to demonstrate one of such events. Using closing reading, it evaluates how elders enabled David's divinely guided meteoric rise to kingship was finally realized because of their controlled detribalized deed and their drive for national integration. The paper, by the passage, joins works and voices calling on Nigerian Traditional Leaders to make the movements needed for national integration. Movement from tribalization to the choosing of a leader who will be the melting point for national integration in order to have sustained growth like happened to Israel after David's choice and coronation in 2 Sam 5:1-5.

Keywords: Tribe, tribalism, David, elders and national integration.

Introduction

2 Sam 7:8-16 reports the divine promise of an eternal dynasty to David.¹ A dynasty that lasted in succession from Solomon² up to the end of the Babylonian exile in 586 BC by Nebuchadnezzar.³ 2 Sam 5:1-5, which is the pericope of this paper, contains the narrative that describes David's institutionalization as king of the whole of Israel by the nation's elders. The eventual enthronement of David by the tribes and elders of Israel laid the foundation for the dynastic promise of 2 Sam 7:8-16 and the sustained growth the nation enjoyed over centuries. This paper does not underscore 2 Sam 5:1-5's narrative of the ceremony of David's invitation by Israel's elders to accept kingship and his eventual coronation as King by them, but directs itself at underlying elements of controlled de-tribalisation by the elders of Israel, which created national integration for the nascent nation of Israel. Their deeds in the passage demonstrates important features of de-tribalisation that Nigeria's traditional leaders could learn from and practice. This paper is premised on the understanding of exegeting the final form of the Hebrew text of 2 Sam 5:1-5. The Hebrew words in the passage shall basically be transliterated. Furthermore, this paper shall employ the synchronic approach with elements of close reading to interpret its pericope for the purpose of calling traditional rulers to work for the integration of the Nigeria.

Conceptual Clarification

Nigerian Traditional Rulers

Traditional Rulers operate within the Nigerian traditional system of authority which Daniel Adetoritse Tonwe and Osa Osemwota contend faces the difficulty of a universally accepted definition, because of the diversity in the political and administrative components of traditional systems in different parts of the country. This difficulty notwithstanding, these scholars define traditional systems of authority "as the indigenous polity which existed before the advent of the colonialists."⁴ This system of authority was headed and managed by traditional rulers across the country. Joseph I. Igwubor describes them "as the leaders of the people and custodian of the people's culture and tradition."⁵ Victor Egwemi and Jacob Akoh William explicate Igwubor's definition by asserting further that: "...a traditional ruler is a person who by virtue of his ancestral background occupies the throne or stool of an area and who has been appointed to it in accordance with the custom and tradition of the area and has suzerainty over the people of that area."⁶

These definitions inform why Igwubor avows that traditional rulers are highly respected and revered by the people within and outside their domain. Their words are laws to the people and their advice and opinions on issues are respected and accepted. This is so, because they are seen as intermediaries between the people and the gods and the ancestors, and as such, cannot be disobeyed or disrespected.⁷ Before independence, the traditional rulers were in firm control of their local councils. They sadly tended to be despotic and authoritarian in performing their functions which were essentially maintenance of law and order, and enforcement of tax policies of the British colonial government.⁸ The political struggles of the pre-Independence era and the changes which emerged from Nigeria's post-Independence developments engendered laws and processes that redefined who traditional rulers are. This led to changes in their place and function within political setups. They became contemporarily useful for the maintenance of peace in their domains and for the resolution of local conflicts within their jurisdiction of leadership.⁹

Daniel Adetoritse Tonwe and Osa Osemwota corroborate this view by asserting that:

The assumption of political power by the military in 1966 had substantial implications for the role of traditional rulers in local government. In the Northern States between 1966 and 1972 Customary/Native Courts were taken over by state governments, and Prisons and Police were taken over by the Federal Government. The nomenclature of Native Authority was dropped and the existing Native Authorities balkanised into independent local government units, but the Emirs were still influential in the decision-making process at the local level. New provisions were introduced for election of two-thirds of the membership of the Local Government Councils. In Western states (including the Mid-west), before 1966, the role of traditional rulers in local government had been essentially ceremonial. The situation was the same in parts of the Eastern States where traditional rulership still existed.¹⁰

Irrespective of the changes that have ensued in the definition of the place and roles of traditional leaders, being holders of an age-long and respected institution, they have the capacity not only to maintain peace and resolve conflicts but also contribute to national integration by their synergized effort at ensuring a national leader of due national acceptance like the tribal leaders in 2 Sam 5:1-5 did. Traditional leaders should pursue this objective in a controlled de-tribalised motive. They should pursue this in the realization that, they will not throw away their particular tribal identities, because they serve as custodians and perpetuators of the customs and traditions of the tribe they represent in every national dialogue and event, but they should do so in the spirit and principle of national good. Expecting that the traditional rulers would de-identify with their ethnicity to elevate to being 'detribalized Nigerians' can amount to delusions that seeks to cleanse them from their long held and time-tested identities and cultural heritage, because ethnic diversity is a blessing rather than a curse. It can be harnessed for development¹¹, especially when ominous parochial interests are set for a bigger good.

Historical and Literary Context 2 Sam 5:1-5

In their final form, the Books of Samuel are, among many matters, a compilation of a certain perspective of David's place and role in Israel's transition from a tribal society to the modest beginnings of monarchical nation¹². The text of 2 Sam 5:1-5 narrates a significant role played by elders in actualizing the fullest expression of it. Against parochial tribal affiliations and interests, they worked on a matter with David that created room for national integration. The historical and larger literary contexts 2 Sam 5:1-5 could explain the reason for their action. The contexts show that tribalisation did not really help them. A brief review and description will elucidate on the argument of this section of this presentation.

After Joshua had led the Israelites into the Promised Land, Judges 17-21 narrates how they coexisted in a loose confederation of tribes where "there was no king in Israel; every man did what was right in his own eyes (17:6; cf. 18:1; 19:1; 21:25)."¹³ This socio-political arrangement has been supposedly termed amphictyony¹⁴. The implication was there was no viable and reliable social order and no legitimated public national structure of governance. The resultant effect of this development was a chaotic, barbaric social practice and a corresponding

doubtful religion depicted as image-generating and idolatrous (Judges 17-18).¹⁵ In this socio-political system and structure, whenever an external enemy army threatened any tribe of Israel, the other tribes will gang up to its aid. At such times, a Judge from any of the tribes is chosen by Yhwh to exercise leadership in a war to defend the attacked tribe. Otherwise, each of the twelve tribes existed separately and had their own tribal leaders, group identity, territory, particular shrines, and traditions. What held the different tribes was two factors: firstly, was their common ancestry because tradition held that the twelve tribes were descendants of the twelve sons of Jacob; secondly was the belief that Yhwh was their king.

Painfully, the tribal confederacy system began to break down as early as the time of Deborah because of less interest in the Confederacy, since in Judges 5:16-19 Deborah chides tribes that didn't respond to the muster to aggregate and defend a threatened tribe. This development implies that the old tribal Confederacy was inadequate in meeting the persistent military threats posed by Israel's neighbors. Hence, the people needed and wanted a king to lead them in battle¹⁶ especially by the threat of the life-and-death relationship being played out between Israel and the Philistines.

From a historical perspective, the immediately foregoing contention was because the Philistines had migrated southward in the twelfth century, but their movement was stopped by the Egyptians. This forced them to settle around the five cities of Ashdod, Ashkelon, Ekron, Gath, and Gaza – later giving their name to Palestine. Their presence and power constituted a threat to the nascent nation called Israel; just as the emerging nation of Israel presented a danger to them. So, the Israelites thinking that the institutionalization of military force led by the king was necessary to survive the threat posed by the Philistines¹⁷, requested for a king. A request account recorded in three separate counts in 1 Samuel (1 Sam 9:1-10:16; 10:17-27; 11:1-15)¹⁸. In two of the three stories demanding for a king, Samuel was directly commanded by God to anoint Saul as king. Thus, kingship is not something to be taken by force or assumed by power: it is a role authorized by Yhwh and conferred by prophetic appointment (1 Sam 10:1; 10:17-27; 11:12-15).

But kingship does not guarantee absolute authority nor is its term of office assured, since once a king proves faithless or disobedient, a prophet is authorized by Yhwh to confront him and can even declare him unfit to rule. This was the case with Saul, who fails twice by disobeying in 1 Sam 13:13-14 and 15:27-28¹⁹. His disobedience brought curse against his kingship, and so David in 1 Sam. 16:1 was anointed king to replace him. This began David's meteoric rise to power culminating 2 Sam 3 – 6.

David's accession to the throne proved to be a complicated, drawn-out, and bloody process. A clear division between the northern tribes and Judah became apparent, since the northern tribes withheld their acknowledgment of his kingship for seven and a half years until the event of 2 Sam 5:1-5. What follows after was a masterful political move in which David chose Jerusalem as his capital city. A neutral city not in the possession of any of the twelve tribes of Israel. Its strategic location on the top of a mountain range made it a place easily defended, so much so that even "the blind and lame" could have held off an attacking army (2 Sam. 5:6-8). In addition to Jerusalem's strategic advantages as a neutral territory between the northern and southern tribes; it also provided access for east—west trade.²⁰ This sharp move by David pointed towards national integration and de-tribalisation in order to enable all under David's rule to feel belonged and welcomed. From the foregoing, we understand that Israel's move from tribal confederacy to asking for a king, was a movement from the tribal system to a drive for national establishment. This was fully realised in the efforts of the tribal leaders in 2 Sam. 5:1-5.

Circumscribing and Structuring 2 Sam 5:1-5

Delimiting 2 Sam 5:1-5

Michael Avioz underscores three verbal markers of a literary unit. He states that a researcher should mark the unit's beginning and the unit's end. He should then shape the unit into a cohesive whole so that its parts are bound together to form an independent, complete, self-contained "package."²¹ Avioz's counsel characterises this paper's circumscription of 2 Sam 5:1-5 as a pericope. 2 Sam. 5:1-5 is first marked out by the *inclusio* establishing

its preceding unit (2 Sam. 4:1-12). This immediate unit, 2 Sam 4:1-12, is distinguished by the proper noun, Abner, which frames it in vv.1.12. The character, Abner, is not mentioned in the text of this paper. Thematically, the preceding unit narrates the death of Ishboshet and the burial of his head in Hebron according to David's order. This theme and the character of Ishboshet are equally not in the pericope of this presentation.

Rather the text of this presentation introduces new characters such as *šēveṭ* meaning "tribes" in v. 1 and *zāqēn* meaning "elder" in v. 5. These lexemes are not found in the preceding passage nor in the following unit from 2 Sam 5:6. The text of this paper thematically presents the meeting of the tribes and elders with David for the purpose of confirming an existing prophecy about David's kingship and then his eventual coronation as king (v. 3). Even though it is difficult to draw out where this unit closes because the statistical information in vv. 4-5 appear to have a transitional function through the mention of both Hebron and Jerusalem, the terms *šēveṭ* and *zāqēn* together with the theme of David's coronation mark out 2 Sam 5:1-5 from its preceding passage and following unit. Secondly, the place name *chebrōn* meaning "Hebron" in vv. 1a and 5a, and the phrase *kol- yisrāē'l* meaning "all Israel" at v. 1a and v. 5c,²² equally demarcate this unit from what precedes and what follows. The circumscribing effort thus far suggests that 2 Sam 5:1-5 is about tribes, elders and the coronation of David by all Israel. These characters and the themes of "all Israel" and "coronation" are among the issues not collocated in the immediately preceding and following texts of this study.

Structure of 2 Sam 5:1-5

Christian Vogel divides 2 Sam. 5:1-5 in tripartite subsections:

- a. the tribes meet David in vv. 1-2,
- b. the covenant and anointing ceremony between the elders and David v. 3
- c. concluding statistical information in vv. 4-5²³.

This structure suggests that the covenant and anointing ceremony between the elders and David is the central concern of the tribes and elders in this unit. Verse 3 collates 2 Sam 5:1-5 well into its immediate context which R. P. Gordon describes as reporting where David was "acknowledged as king by all the tribes of Israel and has taken up residence in Jerusalem, his newly-acquired capital (2 Sam. 5)."²⁴ Respecting v. 3 as showcasing the central matter of 2 Sam 5:1-5 is not the sole direction of this paper. This paper is rather concerned with the symbolic significance of the action of elders on de-tribalisation and national integration. The paper shall albeit follow the outline of Vogel's tripartite division in its exegesis and application of 2 Sam 5:1-5.

Exegesis of 2 Sam 5:1-5 and the Social Implications of the Tribes' and Elders' Deeds

Verses 1-2: Tribes Meet David an Act of Moving Beyond Tribalisation

Verses 1-2 of 2 Sam. 5:1-5 narrate the meet between David and the tribes (*šēveṭ*) at Hebron (*chebrōn*). The verses are introduced by a verbal phrase called *wayyāvo 'ū* meaning "and they came," announcing the movement of the Tribes to meet David at Hebron. The tribes referred to in v. 1a are "... members of the same 'clan'..."²⁵ or "a group of persons or clans with common ancestry"²⁶ through parentage by birth, and so, of common lineage. This description is a cultural construction arising from genealogical descent.²⁷ Biblical history traces the tribes directly to Jacob whose wives gave birth to twelve sons (Gen. 35:22b-26) known as the twelve tribes of Israel. Genesis 49:1-28 lists the names of these tribes: Reuben, Simeon, Levi, Judah, Zebulun, Issachar, Dan, Gad, Asher, Naphtali, Joseph, Benjamin²⁸. Each of the twelve tribes became organized and identified, tracing their descent in ascending order from their family to their patriarchal house and clan to their tribal alliances. These tribal alliances metamorphosed into a people or a state (cf. Dt. 29:17; 10sh. 7:14; 13:29; 1 S. 10:19-20; also, Nu. 4:18; 19s. 21:24; 1 S. 9:21)²⁹. Each of the tribes after settlement in the Land evolved along their territorial groups and primary social organisational units in Israel's social structure, before the establishment of the monarchy. Each tribe had a place as one of the primary segments of the whole people³⁰.

Representatives of these different tribes formed the band which made the movement to meet David at Hebron. These representatives might have been their heads. The contention that tribal heads made up the

delegation is corroborated by David M. Fouts' simple analysis of the term *šēvet* which translates as "tribe". Fouts asserts that *šēvet* "... originally referred to parts of a tree from which a staff or a weapon could be made. Leaders who effectively used these weapons came to be known as *šēvet* (Num. 24:17-19), as did the people following them"³¹. Consequently, even though the most prevalent meaning ascribed to the term *šēvet* in the Old Testament is that of tribe, specifically the tribes of Israel; it theologically signifies authority depicting the rod of discipline or the scepter of Messiah³² wielded by a leader in any guise. From the foregoing semantic analysis, the movement of the Tribes was actually the movement of the leadership of the tribes to David at Hebron.

Furthermore, verse 1's use of the adjective *col*, meaning "all", underlines that all the tribal heads made the movement from their individual territorial enclaves, identities and tribal affiliations to a cause of national importance at Hebron. When they arrived, they made two ground breaking statements which give credibility to their move beyond their individual tribal affiliations. They first of all identified David as their "bone and flesh". A phrase A. A. Anderson exegetes as highlighting kinship relationship (2 Sam 19:13, 14[12, 13]; Gen 29:14) rather than as being part of a covenantal formula.³³ For the tribal elders to identify David as their "bone and flesh" is to speak of bonding unity between all tribal leaders and David. A unity that recognizes them as Israelites. Thus, creating the first element of national integration from this pericope. This common ground of unity is further highlighted by the clause "to lead out and to bring in". Again, A. A. Anderson interprets this clause as belonging to the language of military affairs, and it describes the activities of the chief or leader (cf. Josh 14:11; 1 Sam 18:13, 16; 29:6). The tribal leaders, therefore, underscore that David was leading and bringing in even during Saul's reign. Their point being that David was a "hidden messiah" and leader with an outstanding military success.³⁴

The entire action and words of these tribal leaders did not highlight David's tribe in any way. Their attention was fixed on David's leadership qualities and characteristics. Characteristics that will entrench and promote national orientation and integration. The driving force and guiding principle of Israel's tribal leaders were free from the strangle hold of negative tribal affiliations and identities. These leaders were not tied down by the political autonomy of their societies nor were they characterized by a high degree of arrogant self-sufficiency, distinctive language, culture and sense of identity³⁵ but by a quest for national good. That did not mean they denied their peculiar natural language, thought processes and patterns³⁶ in their quest for national unity.

What these elders did and said in vv. 1-2 should respectively serve as a call and reminder to and of Nigeria's Traditional Leaders. As tribal leaders of people and communities with their peculiar natural language, thought processes and patterns³⁷, they need to make similar mental and tangible physical movements beyond their tribal affiliations to deeds of national interest. To take this giant step will not deny and/or negate their tribal identities, because every Nigerian is a member of one particular tribe. Within that tribe, customs and traditions are established to guide, direct and control the beliefs, attitudes, and habits of its individual members. Failure to comply with the collective will of the tribe will be tantamount to an act of disloyalty which may be punishable with severe penalties. To avert the penalties, obedience to the tribe is thus inculcated in the tribe's folk from childhood.³⁸

The danger that must be guarded against unchecked obedience to one's tribe is that of negative tribalism. Nigerian traditional leaders must realize that when they make their subjects more loyal to their tribe than to their friends, their country, or any other social group³⁹, they engage in ominous tribalism⁴⁰. They must be aware that the art of tribalism is not an unmitigated evil. In fact, it is an anthropological phenomenon of universal facticity and application which cannot be exterminated without committing wholesale genocide to a section of the human race. The traditional leaders have to champion a form of assimilation that is peculiar to Nigeria and does not make them lose their tribal identity and its forms of visible expression.⁴¹

Nnamdi Azikiwe opined that it has worked in countries like British Isles, Switzerland, United States, etc.⁴² The guiding principle for achieving this is nationalism, "an ideology that stresses allegiance to one's nation as a major political virtue and national preservation and self-determination as prime political imperatives. Traditional leaders must be aware that nationalism has proved an immensely powerful force for popular

mobilization over two centuries in almost every part of the world.”⁴³ Hence, traditional leaders must shun every deliberate policy of exclusivism and outright domination of their own tribe over others. The first step to achieving this is the mental and physical movement by leaders who control the grassroots from the old ways of doing things just like their counterparts did in 2 Sam 5:1-2.⁴⁴ This is imperative at times of mobilisations for choosing a leader that will serve as the basis for national integration.

Verse 3: Covenant and Anointing of David by Elders for National Integration

One of the most significant measures for achieving national integration is in a leadership that is borne out of nationalistic spirit and it is ready to pursue, entrench and consolidate national relations across different classes and peoples. Such a leader must be principled on and be ready to promote equality and equity for all and in all irrespective of class and socio-cultural and political identity. Here too, the process of producing such a leader must be championed by Traditional rulers.

As a result, Traditional rulers should not solely advance national integration by being adequate managers of their local land, preservers and perpetuators of cultures and traditions, promoters of the exercise of traditional political system, disseminators of information at grassroots levels⁴⁵, they must mentally and physically make moves to transit from the old ways of doing things. In such bold moves, they liberate themselves from the reductive position of errand boys of political leaders⁴⁶ who have no desire and interest for national integration. All that such political leaders care about is the filling up of their pockets and those of their cronies with the wealth of the nation. Traditional rulers must like the tribal leaders in verses 1-2 identify and demand from seekers of political office the leadership qualities that will empower national integration. Such seekers of political office are to be encouraged into offices. To blame politicians and corruption, to fear the control of all by the ruling class and to decry weak state institutions as factors hindering national integration⁴⁷ is not enough. Traditional Leaders in view of the multi-ethnic nature of Nigeria, are to empower leaderships which will unify Nigeria irrespective of the existing differences in language, culture and traditions to create a harmonious relationship among the diverse groups⁴⁸. Promoting one of such leaders will surely make a difference. This is exactly what the elders (*zāqēnîm*) did in verse 3.

In verse 3, the tribal leaders were eventually and specifically addressed as *zāqēn yišrā'ēl* (elders of Israel). Elders of Israel semantically reflects *šēveṭ yišrā'ēl* (tribes of Israel) of v. 1. This new identification at v. 3 reinforces this paper's earlier interpretation of “tribes” as actually referring to the Traditional Leaders who made a move to meet David at Hebron in v. 1. These same leaders make a second move in v. 3 underlined by the verbal phrase *wayyāvo 'û* meaning “they moved” to indicate their movement again to David to perform two functions: to make a covenant with him and to anoint him King over all Israel.

The Hebrew term *Zāqēn* utilised v. 3 means “elders”. The term is employed in the Old Testament in two ways: to connote old age (Gen. 18:12; 19:31; 25:8; 35:29; 44:20, etc.) and to technically refer to leaders of a community (Gen. 19:4; Lev. 19:32; 1 Sam 28:14; Isa. 19:15[14]; 47:6, etc.). In Ancient Near East Culture, *Zāqēn* described the authority and leadership possessed and exercised by men because of their accumulated wisdom and experience. For this reason, they were to be honoured (Lev. 19:32) and be part of their social political structure. Hence, various Ancient Near East Cultures recognized and honoured them as “elders” among the Egyptians (Gen. 50:7; Psa. 105:22), Moabites and Midianites (Num. 22:4.7), Gibeonites (Josh. 9:11) and Israelites (Exod. 3:16). Thus, as far back as the Egyptian captivity, even the Israelites were led by elders (Exod. 3:16) and it has been accepted that this concept originated in the Hebrew patriarchal family institution. Hence, at the time of the settling of the Promised Land, they were influential on a national level. After the settling, there were national and city leaders with influence on issues bothering the nation. Consequently, in 1 Sam 8:4-5 they pleaded with Samuel to appoint a king when they felt the Judges were not freely capable of protecting them against their enemies. After the appointment, Saul recognized their importance when he begged Samuel to continue to honour him before the elders of the land (1 Sam. 15:30). At the time for the need of a leader who can form national unity and encourage national integration, tribal elders used their wisdom, age, honour and

authority, in v. 3, to go to accept David as king for all Israel. They felt David had the capacity to stand as a symbol and an embodiment of national integration.

To fully achieve their aim, these elders of Israel made a covenant (b^rît) with David. Gordon J. McConville calls it “covenant between human parties”⁴⁹. In this kind of covenant in the Old Testament, treaties or agreements of parity between rulers or powerful individuals are made (Gen. 21:27; 26:28; 31:44; 1 Kin. 5:12[26]; 15:19; 2 Kin. 11:4)⁵⁰. This would have given the elders the grounds to demand for the effective leadership which respects and involves all the tribes of Israel on issues of unity and national growth. They would have demanded for David to equally create rooms and allowances for the integration of all Israelites in the nascent nation, in such a way as to guarantee equity and equality. The possible assurance of David on those expected requests at the covenant making must have led them to anoint (*yayyimš^{ch}û*) him King. An indication that the Saulide dynasty has been rejected and David assumes leadership of a United Kingdom. Their covenant therefore confirms David’s earlier anointing by Samuel (1 Sam. 16:13-14) but goes further to demonstrate an event that even Saul did not enjoy: the fact that all the elders of Israel in unity chose and anointed him. Saul simply got the anointing of Samuel. These deeds by elders of Israel meet an important aspect of national integration, which is their conscious and deliberate efforts for the attainment of coordination and harmony within Israel under David. The elders of Israel did not allow parochial tribal sentiments, nepotism and all other vices to polarize them and consequently the people⁵¹. No wonder Christian Vogel asserts that David’s kingship is not associated with absolute and arbitrary power but rather with serving and caring for the people as a faithful steward entrusted with the position by Yhwh and is therefore responsible to Him.⁵²

Nigeria’s traditional rulers should learn from and emulate the elders of Israel. Their learning should enlighten them to act like the elders. This has become imperative because it seems as if all efforts at integrating and building up Nigeria as a nation appear to have failed to achieve the desired results largely because of leadership failure. Chiefly championed by visionless leaders with the sharply bent inclination to pursue their ethnic and personal agenda rather than national unity and growth. It is even held that two of the founding fathers were wholly guilty of it. In fact, his book “Path to Nigeria Freedom, published in 1947, Chief Obafemi Awolowo expressed disbelief in the Nigerian project and national unity, and opined that, “Nigeria is not a nation, it is a mere geographical expression. There are no Nigerians in the same sense as there are English or Welsh or France (French)”⁵³. The implication of this assertion is that, the fact that different ethnic groups live in one national boundary called Nigeria, they can never have one national identity as “Nigerians”⁵⁴. Traditional Rulers can rewrite that narrative and give such notion a refined perspective. This is because contemporary Nigeria needs to transcend this myopic and parochial limitations if she must grow into an enviable nation. The principles of merit and equity should shape the orientation of Nigeria, going forward. It should be done without a loss of the individual ethnic identities that shape her. The determination of the process can be handled by eminent social scientists in the nation. This call for national integration is encouraged by content of the last verses of 2 Sam 5:1-5.

Verses 4-5: Concluding Statistical Information Expressing Need for National Integration

Verses 4-5 are a formulaic expression of a protracted and productive period of the united monarchy⁵⁵. They explicate that David came to occupy Israelites’ most powerful political position when he “was thirty years old” (v. 4). The total number of years he governed as king over any part of Israel was “forty years”: seven and a half of those years was “over Judah” while he was “in Hebron” (v. 5) and “thirty-three years,” were spent “in Jerusalem,” from which David “reigned over all Israel and Judah.” This summary presentation showed what happens when a good leader with national interest sits in governance. In fact, this proleptic mention of David reigning as king in Jerusalem anticipates the narrative of vv. 6–9, where David’s first act as king over all Israel was the establishment of a capital city in northern territory.⁵⁶ A neutral geographical location which will not cause dissensions among the tribes. This started the process of David’s acceptance by all and his long reign up to age of seventy.⁵⁷

All those were achieved by the elders whose positive influence never abated well into David's reign (1 Sam. 17:4.15; 1911[12]). The gains of their intervention in 2 Samuel 5:1-5 sustained in David's successors (Solomon – 1 Kin. 8:1-3; Ahab – 20:7; Jezebel - 21:8; Jehu – 2 Kgs 10:1; Hezekiah 19:2; Josiah – 23:1). His progeny perpetuated the dynasty promised him in 2 Sam 7:8-16. They made sure of it through all manners of political hurdles and threats, religious problems and socio-cultural storms up to the sad and eventual end of kingship in Israel by the invasions of Emperor Nebuchadnezzar in 596 and 586 BC. Luckily, the invasion is believed to have only ended the physical expression of Davidic dynasty, because Christian tradition interprets it as continued in Christ (Mt 1:1-18 and Acts 2:3ff).⁵⁸

Furthermore, the larger literary context of 2 Sam 5:1-5 is much of 1-2 Samuel. This context clearly reflects Israel's transformation from a loose association of tribes into a centralised nation governed by a monarch.⁵⁹ Walter Brueggemann captures it thus:

The Books of Samuel are the narrative rendering of Israel's move from tribal chaos and barbarism to monarchic legitimacy and bureaucratic ruthlessness. The historical achievement of Israel in the course of this decisive and irreversible transition is a remarkable one and should not be underestimated. Israel has been in the process of building public structures of legitimacy and institutions of accountability and order. While the narrative tends to focus on personalities, this larger public agenda is crucial.⁶⁰

The elders initiated and invariably catalyzed this direction of development and growth in Israel. They understood that many nations of the Ancient Near East, especially around the twelfth century, interpreted monarchy as the natural social structure that had existed for all time⁶¹ and so knew that Israel needed it as well. They were futuristic, unbiased and selfish in their eventual choice of David as king of national recognition.

Conclusion

This paper is protreptic in feature. It takes the example of 2 Sam 5:1-5 to remind Nigeria's traditional leaders that "unity, welfare and primacy of public interest were among the community-oriented values of the past under the supervision of the traditional rulers."⁶² Contemporary Traditional Rulers are to work for it because Abubakar Zaria Ibrahim asserts that "the advantages which accrue to a united society, the value of consensus and the importance of giving primacy to the interests of the people rather than those of a section are as valid for contemporary Nigeria as they were for the pre-colonial Nigeria."⁶³ Traditional rulers can commence the process of national integration in a detribalized social structure in the quality of leaders they empower by their deeds. Where this does not really happen, Nigeria will not achieve the growth commensurate with her powers, natural endowments and quality of human capital resources. Lettered minds have rightly from the early years of the nation's history identified that the biggest problem in Nigeria is her leaders.

Therefore, repeated research works calling for credible leaders by various media cannot know end. If the Bible is the only inanimate objective with living cells, it is of importance here as a model for this call. It contains the experiences of human beings within history, geographical locations and cultural orientations like Nigeria's. Whatever solutions were proffered in the Bible is applicable to Nigeria's. Humanity has largely faced the same problem. The same historical situation. This paper did not go into deep and technical definition of terms like detribalisation and national integration. This paper's interpretation of those terms is implied in the explanations given and the contextualization of the actions of the elders of Israel.

Endnotes

¹Michael Avioz, "The Davidic Covenant in 2 Samuel 7: Conditional or Unconditional?" in Gershon Galil and Ayelet Gilboa and Aren M. Maeir and Dan'el Kahn, eds., *The Ancient Near East in the 12th-10th Centuries BCE Culture and History: Proceedings of the International Conference held at the University of Haifa, 2-5 May, 2010*, (Münster: Ugarit-Verlag, 2012), 43-51.

²Marcin Konarski “A Political Upheaval as a Form of Succession of the Royal Power in the United Monarchy of Israel. From Saul to Solomon,” *Studia Luridica Lublinensia* XXVII (4) (2018), 61-66.

³George A. Barton, “Influence of the Babylonian Exile on the Religion of Israel”, *The Biblical World* 37 (6) (June 1911), 369.

⁴Daniel Adetoritse Tonwe and Osa Osemwota, “Traditional Rulers and Local Government in Nigeria: A Pathway to Resolving the Challenge,” *Commonwealth Journal of Local Governance* 13/14 (November 2013), 130.

⁵Joseph I. Igwubor, “Traditional Institution and Nation Building: The Role of Traditional Rulers in the Maintenance of National Security for Sustainable Development”, *UJAH* 21/4, (2020), 203.

⁶Victor Egwemi and Jacob Akoh William, “A Critical Analysis of the Role of Traditional Chiefs/Rulers in Contemporary Nigeria,” *The Nigerian Journal of Research and Production* 11/4 (December, 2007), 149.

⁷Igwubor, 203.

⁸Adetoritse and Osemwota, 131.

⁹Joseph I. Igwubor, “Traditional Institution and Nation Building” 203-214; Abubakar Zaria Ibrahim, “The Role of Traditional Rulers: Nigeria’s Emirs and Chiefs in Conflict Management Since 1976”, in Isaac Olawale Albert and Is-haq Olanrewaju Oloyede, eds., *Dynamics of Peace of Process*, (Centre for Peace and Strategic Studies, University of Ilorin: Ilorin, 2010), 238-49.

¹⁰Adetoritse and Osemwota, “Traditional Rulers and Local Government in Nigeria”, 133.

¹¹Onuh Paul Ani, Ike Chinedu Cyril and Nnaji Daniel Ikechi, “Detribalization, Identity and National Development”, *African Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research* 2/2, (2019), 43.

¹²Walter Brueggemann, *An Introduction to the Old Testament: The Canon and Christian Imagination*, (John Knox Press: Kentucky, 2003), 132.

¹³Thomas L. Leclerc, *Introduction to the Prophets: Their Stories, Sayings and Scrolls*, (New York: Paulist Press, 2007), 64.

¹⁴For a brief discussion on amphictyony refer Jacob Weingreen, “The Theory of the Amphictyony in Pre-Monarchical Israel” *Janes* 5 (1973), 427-433.

¹⁵Walter Brueggemann, “Samuel, Book of 1-2”, in David Noel Freedman, ed., *The Anchor Bible Dictionary* V, (New York – London – Toronto – Sydney – Auckland: Doubleday, 1992), 966.

¹⁶Thomas, 64.

¹⁷Anthony Campbell and Mark O’Brien, “1-2 Samuel” in William R. Farmer, ed., *The International Bible Commentary: A Catholic and Ecumenical Commentary for the Twenty-First Century*, (Minnesota: The Liturgical Press, 1998), 573.

¹⁸Enock Okode, “Theocracy in Crisis: A Contextual Study of 1 Samuel 8:4-18 with Practical Reflection for Today,” *Africa Journal of Evangelical Theology* 27/2 (2008), 137-154.

¹⁹Leclerc, 66.

²⁰Consolidating the political importance of Jerusalem, David established the city as the center of the kingdom’s religious life. He did this by moving into the city the central symbol of Yahwistic faith—the Ark of the Covenant. The Ark contained the tablets of the Ten Commandments (Dent 10:5), which were “written with the finger of God” (Exod. 31:18). The presence of the Ark in Jerusalem made the city the chief cult center of the kingdom. Politically and religiously, then, Jerusalem became the heart of the kingdom. The seat of political power was David’s palace (2 Sam, 5:11-12), but there was no comparable site in which the Ark of the Covenant could dwell. Once David had been given “rest from all his enemies around him” (2 Sam 7:1), he set out to rectify this unseemly inequity, for it was not right that an earthly king should dwell in a fine house of cedar, while the Ark of the heavenly king was kept in a tent. David informs the court prophet, Nathan, that he intends to build a “house” for Yhwh’s dwelling (Thomas L. Leclerc, *Introduction to the Prophets*, 72).

²¹Michael Avioz, “The Literary Structure of the Books of Samuel: Setting the Stage for a Coherent Reading”, *Currents in Biblical Research* (CBR) 16(1) (2017), 8-33.

²²Christian Vogel, “The Nature of David’s Kingship at Hebron: An Exegetical and Theological Study of 2 Samuel 2:1-5:5” (PhD Dissertation, Andrews University, June 2019) 281.

²³*Ibid.*, 282.

²⁴Gordon, R. P., *1 & 2 Samuel*, (Sheffield: Sheffield Academic Press, 1998), 61.

²⁵This perception of a tribe relates to classification in a patrilineal society like Israel’s. Consequently, two siblings are related because of a common father, two cousins by a common grandfather, two tribesmen by a common Ancestor of the tribe and two Israelites by common descent from the ancestor, Israel, father of the twelve tribes (Ronald Hendel, *Remembering Abraham: Culture, Memory, and History in the Hebrew Bible*, (Oxford: Oxford university press, 2005), 10).

²⁶Rudi A Meir and Don Scott, “Tribalism: definition, identification and relevance to the marketing of professional sports franchises” *International Journal of Sports Marketing & Sponsorship* (July 2007), 334.

²⁷Genealogical descent and alliances are one of the ways ancient Israelites were joined together. In doing so, they defined who an Israelite was and who was an outsider (Ronald Hendel, *Remembering Abraham*, 9.10).

²⁸Carol J. Dempsey, “Tribe,” in Carroll Stuhlmueller, editor, *The Collegeville Pastoral Dictionary of Biblical Theology*, (Bangalore: Theological Publications in India, 2011), 1018; it is generally assumed the tribes were twelve, but there are arguments against this conservative number. Views hold that the tribes were more than twenty. For further research on this contentious matter refer Frank S. Frick “Tribe,” in Paul J. Achtemeier, editor, *Harper’s Bible Dictionary*, (Bangalore: Theological Publications in India, 1994),

1097. However, the ideal designation of the number of the tribes as twelve became common knowledge by the Qumran period. From that era, the designation became socio-politically important, because each tribe became the largest organizational unit of the people subdivided in clans (1 QSa 1: 15). At that time, “Leaders of the tribes” were mentioned (1 QSa 1:29; cf. IQM 2:3; 4QMd 1:2) and the number of tribes, of course, was twelve (IQM 2:3 par. 4QMd 5-6; IQM 3:14; IIQT 21:2; cf. also 4QMo 1-3,8-9; IIQT 18:16), which includes “all the tribes of Israel” (1 QM 2:7) and field standards are inscribed with the names of the tribal princes (3: 14-15 par. 4QM f 10:5-6; cf. also 5: 1-2). Furthermore, in times of war, strong men were chosen from all the tribes (2:7) like in the period of the Judges (H-J Zobel “šēveṭ” in G. Johannes Botterweck – Helmer Ringgren – Heinz-Josef Fabry, eds., *Theological Dictionary of the Old Testament XIV*, William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, Grand Rapids – Cambridge, 2004, 310).

²⁹Zobel “šēveṭ”, 306.307.

³⁰Frick “Tribe”, 1097.

³¹David M. Fouts, “šēveṭ” in Willem A. VanGemeren, ed., *New International Dictionary of Old Testament Theology and Exegesis IV*, (Grand Rapids: Zondervan, 1997), 27.

³²Fouts, “šēveṭ”, 27.

³³Anderson, A. A., *Word Biblical Commentary: 2 Samuel*, (Dallas: Word Incorporated, 2002), 75.

³⁴Anderson, A. A.: *Word Biblical Commentary*, 75.

³⁵Carol Lentz, “‘Tribalism’ and Ethnicity in Africa”, *Cali. Sci. Hum.* 31(2) (1995), 316.

³⁶Babatunde Oyediji, “Managing Tribalism within Nigeria’s Democratic Challenges”, *Modern Applied Science* 11/11 (2017), 49.

³⁷Babatunde Oyediji, “Managing Tribalism within Nigeria’s Democratic Challenges”, 49.

³⁸Azikiwe, N. (1964). “Tribalism: A Pragmatic Instrument for National Unity”, retrieved from <https://www.blackpast.org/global-african-history/1964-nnamdi-azikiwe-tribalism-pragmatic-instrument-national-unity/>, September 27th 2022.

³⁹Babatunde Oyediji, “Managing Tribalism within Nigeria’s Democratic Challenges”, 49.

⁴⁰Carol Lentz, “‘Tribalism’ and Ethnicity in Africa”, 307.

⁴¹Nnamdi Azikiwe, “Tribalism”.

⁴²Ibid.

⁴³John Kane, “Nationalism” in Michael Gibbons, ed., *Encyclopedia of Political Thought*, (pp.http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/book/10.1002/9781118474396) Edition 1: Wiley & Sons, 2014), 1.

⁴⁴Azikiwe.

⁴⁵Abdullahi Garba and Ibrahim Mohammed Jirgi and Jummai Mamman and El-Rufa’I Tijjani Abdullahi, “Traditional Instructions and National Integration for Sustainable Development in Nigeria”, *European Journal of Business and Management*, 10(33) (2018), 54.

⁴⁶Abdullahi Garba and Ibrahim Mohammed Jirgi and Jummai Mamman and El-Rufa’I Tijjani Abdullahi, “Traditional Instructions and National Integration for Sustainable Development in Nigeria”, 55.

⁴⁷Onifade Comfort Adenike and Imhonopi David, “Towards National Integration in Nigeria: Jumping the Hurdles”, *Research on Humanities and Social Science* 3 (9) (2013), 78-79.

⁴⁸Samuel B. Kalagbor and Deinibiteim M. Harry, “Leadership Failure and National Integration in Nigeria: Implication for National Building”, *Global Journal of Political Science and Administration*, 8 (3) (July 2020), 48.

⁴⁹Gordon J. McConville, “zāpēn” in Willem A. VanGemeren, ed., *New International Dictionary of Old Testament Theology and Exegesis I*, (Grand Rapids, Zondervan, 1997), 748.

⁵⁰Gordon J. McConville, “zāpēn”, 748.

⁵¹Samuel B. Kalagbor and Deinibiteim M. Harry, “Leadership Failure and National Integration in Nigeria: Implication for National Building”, *Global Journal of Political Science and Administration*, 8/3 (July 2020), 49.

⁵²Christian Vogel, 283-284.

⁵³Kalagbor and Harry, 56.

⁵⁴Ibid.

⁵⁵Verses 4-5 have been argued not be part of the original parts of the Deuteronomists’ framework of Samuel-Kings, but were instead very late additions to the text in the spirit of the authentically Deuteronomistic notices that pertain to the reigns of the kings of the divided monarchy (McCarter, P. Kyle, Jr: *II Samuel: A New Translation with Introduction, Notes, and Commentary*, (New Haven; London: Yale University Press, 2008), 133.

⁵⁶Bergen, Robert D., *I, 2 Samuel*, (electronic ed. Nashville: Broadman & Holman Publishers, 2001), 319.

⁵⁷Smith Henry Preserved, *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on the Books of Samuel*, (New York: C. Scribner’s Sons, 1899), 286.

⁵⁸Paul D. Wegner, “zāpēn” in Willem A. VanGemeren, ed., *New International Dictionary of Old Testament Theology and Exegesis I*, (Grand Rapids, Zondervan, 1997), 1134-1135.

⁵⁹Anthony Campbell and Mark O’Brien, “1-2 Samuel,” 573.

⁶⁰Brueggemann, 132.

⁶¹Campbell and O'Brien, 573.

⁶²Abubakar, 246.

⁶³Ibid.